

Medicinal Insights from Experience, Research, and Knowledge

*A Research-Backed, Experience-Informed Reference Guide to Commonly Used Drugs in Daily
Practice*

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Contents

Medicinal Insights from Experience, Research, and Knowledge

A guide to commonly used over-the-counter medicines and drugs pharmacists frequently deal with.

Sections:

1. Description

An overview of each condition and its symptoms.

2. Medicine / Drug

List of commonly prescribed or dispensed medicines.

3. Commonly Used Brands

Most popular or accessible pharmaceutical brand names.

4. Causes

Frequently encountered causes or contributing factors.

References:

Book: IAP (In A Page)

Authors: Scott Kahan & Ellen G. Smith

Online Sources:

Wikipedia and other accurate, verified online research.

Author's Note:

This document/Handbook of common medicines is primarily based on my practical experience as an assistant pharmacist/pharmacist working in a pharmacy/medical store for over 7 years. It combines hands-on insights with reference materials to provide accurate and useful guidance on everyday medications.

Pharmacist (Myself)

Most of the people in India visit a pharmacy or a medical store even before visiting a doctor if they have any disease, fever or any other medical problem. This makes the job & role of a pharmacist very much important & also responsible job.

→ Even though we dispense the medicines according to the prescription & order of the doctor, we have almost complete knowledge of the medicines like their usage, interactions, effects & side effects.

→ For me the work, the profession of pharmacy is very much adorable, joyful work —the work I am most interested in because I have spent almost seven & half years in a pharmacy till now (24-7-25).

→ When a patient returns, for whom I dispensed medicines—& over-the-counter medicines—and says that he is cured by those medicines, that is my real job satisfaction; my patients'/customers' well-being is my first happiness.

The prime reason for writing this document, practical, research work is that it would help me make a practicing pharmacist's practice in dealing with the patients & also help in making things smoother in pharmacy operations.

This research/data assignment includes a small summary of diseases/disorders which a pharmacist has to go through in context of dispensing over-the-counter medications.

It consists of some of the very common day-to-day medicines, drugs & formulations which are required to be given by a pharmacist on duty.

All these data/knowledge is solely collected from my studies of pharmacy, i.e., pharmacology, anatomy, physiology, medicinal chemistry & many more. Few are researched from Wikipedia, the book IAP & most importantly from my field experience in pharmacy store, from the patients I dealt with.

Schedule H, H1, and X drugs in India are subject to strict regulations. These drugs can only be prescribed by a registered medical practitioner and dispensed by a registered pharmacist. This ensures proper medical oversight and prevents misuse of these medications.

Key Regulations and Guidelines:

Prescription Requirement:

A valid prescription from a registered medical practitioner (doctor) is mandatory for purchasing Schedule H, H1, and X drugs.

Pharmacist's Role:

Registered pharmacists are the only individuals authorized to dispense these drugs.

Record Keeping:

15 Most Important Things to Remember to Become a Better Pharmacist

1. Treat the patient/customer as your friend/family — then you will enjoy your work.
2. Be honest, professional & punctual.
3. Be careful while handling prescriptions.
4. Let the customer/patient speak; listen thoroughly.
5. Never dispense expired prescriptions — they may be misused.
6. Be careful, very careful with older patients/customers; more care required.
7. Never be angry with a patient even if he is at fault.
8. Keep your pharmacy clean; it's your 2nd home.
9. Always check the expiry of medications before dispensing them.
10. If you are unable to identify the name of a medicine — try contacting doctor/hospital; if not, seek the help of a senior.
11. Daily stock checking, inventory audit.
12. Be careful with maintaining records of Schedule H¹ & Schedule X drugs.
13. Respect co-workers & officials.
14. Always guide & help your juniors.
15. Always keep studying, researching the subjects.

1) ABDOMINAL PAIN – pain from inside the abdomen

- May also be near chest or groin, mild to severe

- Cramping may also occur

MEDICINE/DRUG – most commonly used drugs are:

1. Dicyclomine (combination with paracetamol) → Cyclopam tablet, Colimex tablet

2. Mefenamic acid (combination with dicyclomine) → Meftal SPAS tablet, Spasmonil

Plus tablet

Duration – Normally abdominal pain lasts few hours

Most common causes:

- Constipation

- Food allergies

- Food poisoning

2) ALLERGIES – can be seasonal allergies; change in the normal appearance of the skin (rashes; itchy, red skin).

Seasonal allergies include rubbing of eyes, sneezing, running nose, discomfort or itchy throat.

Commonly Used Allergy Medicines

MEDICINE / DRUG: Most commonly used drugs are

1. MONTELUKAST + FEXOFENADINE

-> Montair FX (tablet)

-> Allegra M (tablet)

2. Levocetirizine 5 mg

-> Levocet (tablet)

-> Levorid (tablet)

3. HYDROXYZINE HYDROCHLORIDE

-> Atarax 25 mg SOS (tablet)

-> Atarax long (tablet)

To avoid skin from becoming dry, moisturising lotions like Vaseline lotion can be used

Dewsoft (lotion)

Duration: upto a week or more or may be few hours.

SEASONAL ALLERGIES

MEDICINE / DRUG: Most commonly used drugs are

1. LEVOCETIRIZINE

Commonly Used Allergy Medicines

-> Levocet (tablet), Levorid (tablet)

2. CETIRIZINE

-> Okacet (tablet), Cetzine (tablet)

-> Cetzgel (capsule)

Commonly Used Allergy Medicines

5) MONTELUKAST + LEVOCETIRIZINE

-> Montel LC (tablet)

-> Monticope (tablet)

6) MONTELUKAST + FEXOFENADINE

-> Montair FX (tablet)

-> Allegra M (tablet)

Duration: few hours to two days

Most common causes:

1. Dust particles
2. Allergens
3. Molds

3) WOUNDS

- The cuts, scrapes, scratches, or broken skin due to an accident, bruises, crush injury

MEDICINE / DRUG: Most commonly used general first aid must be given,

cleaning it with povidone-iodine (liquid Betadine) using a cotton.

Then ointments should be applied.

OINTMENTS (commonly used)

1. POVIDONE IODINE + METRONIDAZOLE

- Metrogyl-P (ointment)
- CiplaDine M (ointment)

2. FUSIDIC ACID

- Fucidine (cream)
- Fusi 4 (cream)

Further medicines (antibiotics can be used)

(Amoxicillin + Potassium Clavulanate)

- Augmentin 625 (tablet)
- Megamox-LB 625 (tablet)

Pain medicines only

1. Ibuprofen + Paracetamol

- Imol Plus (tablet)
- Combiflam (tablet)

2. Aceclofenac + Paracetamol + Seratiopeptidase

- Zerodol SP (tablet)
- Nimulid SP (tablet)

Duration: It may take a few days to heal the wound-looked ahead depending upon the severity of the wound.

BODY PAIN = unpleasant feeling in the body.

Can be anywhere between head to toe.

MEDICINE/DRUG: Most common medicines used are:

- Paracetamol
- Dolo 650 (tablet)
- Calpol 650 (tablet)

- Aceclofenac + Paracetamol
- Acemiz Plus (tablet)
- Acecloplus (tablet)
- Hifenac-P (tablet)

- Ibuprofen + Paracetamol
- Combiflam (tablet)
- Imol Plus (tablet)

Duration: Usually lasts few hours

Most common causes:

- Injury (minor)
- Overuse of muscles
- Infections
- Lack of sleep

Extracted Medical Notes

8. Constipation

A kind of digestive complaint where the stools do not pass easily, mostly very painful.

- Medicine/Drugs used are (most common):

- Stool Softeners / Laxatives

- Cremalax (Syrup)

- Cremaffin (Syrup)

- Duphalac (Syrup)

- Cremalax (Tablet)

- Softovac (Granules)

- Most common causes:

- Fiber deficiency

- Dehydration

- Consuming large amount of milk products

6. Cough

It may be 2 types:

(1) Wet Cough

Cough associated with sputum, feels like something stuck in throat & chest.

- Medicine/Drugs:

- Antihistamines

- Levosalbutamol

- Guaiphenesin

- Ambroxol

Examples:

- Ascoril LS (Syrup)

- Bro-Zedex (Syrup)

- Tudy X (Syrup)

(2) Dry Cough

Examples:

- Kuff Q (Tablet)

- M-Solvin (Tablet)

6. DRY COUGH

Cough without mucus, called as unproductive cough

MEDICINE / DRUG

Antihistamines / Decongestants / Expectorants

- Reswas (Syrup)
- Alex (Syrup)
- TusQ DX (Syrup)

WET COUGH COMMON CAUSES

- Infections
- Allergies

Normally lasts 3 to 5 days or 10 days.

DRY COUGH COMMON CAUSES

- Infections
- Allergies
- Asthma

Normally lasts up to a week or 3 weeks.

7. Diarrhea (Motions)

Increased volume of bowel movements, resulting in water loss & dehydration.

Note:

Rehydration should be encouraged along with the medication.

Medicine and Condition Summary

9. MEDICINE / DRUGS:

- Loperamide
- Eldoper (Tablet)
- Antacid (Tablet)
- Ofloxacin + Ornidazole
- O2 (Tablet)
- Oflaz-OZ (Tablet)

Most common causes:

- Infections
- Food issues

Treatment:

- Normally lasts 1 to 3 days

8. DRY SKIN:

Most commonly referred as Xerosis. Skin becomes dry, itchy. Often normal to intense itching, mostly on legs. Moisturisers should be used to feel better. Avoid harsh soaps.

MEDICINE / DRUGS:

Emollients

- Petroleum Jelly
- Cetaphil

Moisturisers

Medicine and Condition Summary

- Venusia

- Cetaphil

Levocetirizine

- Levocet (Tablet)

- Levorid (Tablet)

Duration - 2 week or more

Most common causes:

- Climate
- Eczema, Psoriasis
- Aging

9) Ear Pain

-> Pain or inflammation in the ear canal may or may not be associated with infection. Common in children.

MEDICINE / DRUG

NSAIDS

- Ibuprofen + Paracetamol
- Combiflam (tablet)
- Ibugesic Plus (tablet)
- Naproxen
- Naprosyn (tablet)
- Aceclofenac + Paracetamol
- TIDENAC-P (tablet)
- Zerodol-P (tablet)

Antibiotics (if infection)

- Otogesic (ear drops)
- Dewax (ear drops)
- Candi Biotic (ear drops)

15. Duration of Ear Pain

- Duration: Usually lasts 24 to 48 hours to 3 days
- Most common reasons are:
 - Infection
 - Injury
 - Earwax buildup
 - Sinus infections

16. FEVER

- Definition: Feeling unwell with a rise in normal body temperature
- Normally lasts: 3 to 5 days
- Most common reasons are:
 - Infections
 - Allergies

MEDICINE / DRUG

1) Paracetamol

- Dolo 650mg (Tablet)
- Calpol (Tablet)
- Crocin 650 (Tablet)

2) Aceclofenac + Paracetamol

- Zerodol-P (Tablet)
- Hifenac-P (Tablet)
- Nuhenz-P (Tablet)

3) Other

- Frumil (Tablet)

16. Gastritis / Acidity:

A burning ache or pain in the stomach.

MEDICINE / DRUG

ANTACIDS

- Pantoprazole
- Pan 40 (Tablet)
- Pangraf (Tablet)
- Pantosec (Tablet)

- Omeprazole
- Omez (Capsule)

- Rabeprazole
- Razo (Tablet)
- Rabium (Tablet)
- Rabiwit (Tablet)

Also, these can be given along with the combination of Domperidone:

- Razo-D (Capsule)
- Pan-D (Capsule)
- Omez-D (Capsule)
- Nexpro-RD (Capsule)

Most common reasons are:

- Spicy foods
- Carbonated drinks

- Lack of sleep

12. HEADACHE

- Pain or pressure in the head
- Usually sharp/hollow
- Very common condition

MEDICINE / DRUGS

1. Paracetamol

- Dolo (Tablet)
- Calpol (Tablet)
- Crocin (Tablet)

2. Aceclofenac + Paracetamol

- Zerodol-P (Tablet)
- Hifenac-P (Tablet)

3. Diclofenac + Paracetamol

- Diclowin (Tablet)
- Dicimol (Tablet)

NSAIDs

- Imol plus (Tablet)
- Combiflam (Tablet)
- Naprosyn (Tablet)
- Brufen (Tablet)
- Aceclo (Tablet)
- Zerodol (Tablet)

Usually lasts for few hours to few days

Common reasons include:

- Stress
- Dehydration
- Migraine
- Eye strain
- Infections

18. HEMORRHOIDS (Piles)

- Very common
- Leads to bleeding of anal tissues
- Veins become swollen
- Very painful

MEDICINE / DRUG

- High fiber diet must be recommended

STOOL SOFTENERS

1. DUPHALAC (Syrup)
2. Cremaffin (Syrup)
3. Himalaya Pilex (Tablet)

4. Calcium Dobesilate
 - Logisil (Capsule)
 - Dobesil (Capsule)

Pain Management - Tablets

- Aceclo Plus
- Combiflam
- Ibugesic Plus

They usually last few days to longer

Most common reasons include:

- Aging
- Constipation
- Pregnancy
- Family history

Medical Notes

(19) BACK PAIN: pain felt in the back

- Muscle strain

MEDICINE / DRUG

1. NSAIDS

- Combiflam (tablet)
- Naprosyn (tablet)

2. Acetaminophen

- Tylenol (tablet)

3. Muscle Relaxants

- Zoridol-SP (tablet)
- Zerodol-TH (tablet)

4. Aceclofenac+Thiocolchicoside

- ACMR (tablet)

- Pain relief gel like Volitra, Moove, Omnigel

It can last few days to weeks

Most common reasons include:

- Age
- Weight gain
- Sedentary lifestyle
- Arthritis
- Lack of exercise

Medical Notes

(20) NAUSEA/VOMITING: Feeling of sickness in the stomach and urge to vomit. May result in dehydration.

MEDICINE / DRUG

1. Domperidone
2. Domstal (tablet)
3. Vomistop (tablet)
4. Vomikind (tablet)
5. Ondem (tablet)
6. Zofran (tablet)
7. Emset (tablet)

Usually it lasts 24 hours to 2 days

Most common reasons are

1. Food poisoning
2. Motion sickness
3. Stomach flu
4. Migraine

(16) NECKACHE: Stiff neck or intense pain around neck area

MEDICINE / DRUG

1. Ibuprofen + Paracetamol
2. Combiflam (tab)
3. Imol plus (tab)
4. Aceclo plus (tab)
5. Aceclofenac + Paracetamol
6. Hifenac-P (tab)
7. Aceclo & parac (tab)
8. Naprosyn (tab)
9. Diclofenac + Paracetamol
10. Diclowin plus (tab)
11. Diclomol (tab)

Most common reasons:

- Muscle strain
- Wrong sleeping position
- Injuries

Usually it lasts few hours to 3 days.

Oral Ulcers (mouth ulcers) - Very common & painful. (Burns, sores to the tongue or other parts in the mouth.)

MEDICINE / DRUG

1. Orasore (gel)
2. Smyle (gel)
3. Zylra L (gel)
4. Mucopain (gel)

Usually it lasts up to a week

-> Most common reasons:

- Accidental biting of inside of cheek
- Burns from eating hot food
- Viral infections
- Vitamin deficiency

RED EYE (CONJUNCTIVITIS)

Inflammation & infection of the outer membrane of the eyeball or inner membrane. Very common & painful.

-> It is contagious if caused by bacteria or viruses.

MEDICINE / DRUG

1. MOXIFLOXACIN
 - Moxicip (eye drops)
 - Moxiblu (eye drops)

23. CIPROFLOXACIN

- Ciplox (eye drops)
- Cipwel (eye drops)

3. OFLOXACIN

- Oflin (eye drops)
- Ofloxacin (eye drops)

4. Carboxymethylcellulose

- Refresh Tears (eye drops)

Most common reasons:

1. Bacterial or viral infections
2. Irritants such as chemicals

Can last up to a week

19. PAINFUL LEGS

Many reasons & very common. Feeling pain or discomfort in the legs. Can also be a burning sensation.

MEDICINE/DRUG

ACETAMINOPHEN

- Tylenol (tablet)

2) Ibuprofen

- Brufen (tablet)
- Advil (tablet)

1) Aceclofenac + Paracetamol

- Nelnac P (tablet)
- Hifenac P (tablet)
- Zerodol P (tablet)

Usually it lasts 1-10 3 days

Most common reasons include:

- Injuries
- Muscle fatigue
- Dehydration
- Tight calf muscles
- Overuse

20) Sore Throat: Very common & painful

Scratch or burning feeling in the throat.

MEDICATION / DRUGS

ANTIBIOTICS

AZITHROMYCIN

- 1) Azikem (tablet)
- 2) Azivent (tablet)
- 3) Azithral (tablet)
- 4) Azax (tablet)

ERYTHROMYCIN

- Erythro (tablet)
- Althrocin (tablet)

Pain management:

- Acetaminophen
- Tylenol (tablet)
- Naproxen
- Naprosyn (tablet)

Aceclofenac + Paracetamol

- Acemiz Plus (tablet)
- Hifenac P (tablet)

Gargle with warm salt water must be encouraged

Usually sore throat lasts 1 to 5 days.

Most common causes:

- Viral infection
- Allergies

Toothache & Urine Infection Notes

Toothache

- Mostly tooth pain lasts a few hours to a week.

Common reasons include:

- Tooth decay
- Gum disease
- Infections
- Decay

Urine Infection

- Very common
- Burning sensation or infection in any part of the urinary tract. Usually painful.

Medicine / Drug:

- Oral solution (citric acid & potassium citrate)

1. K-Cit (syrup)

2. Urine alkaliser (liquid)

- Disodium hydrogen citrate

3. Citra alk (syrup)

4. Cital (syrup)

Toothache (continued)

- Normal or intense pain in the teeth or tooth. May or may not be due to infection.

Medicine / Drug

If infection, treat with antibiotics:

Amoxycillin:

- Novamox (tablet)
- Mox (tablet)
- Almox (tablet)

Trimethoprim + Sulphamethoxazole:

- Bactrim DS (tablet)
- Septrim DS (tablet)

Clindamycin (if severe):

- Dalacin (tablet)
- Dalachel (tablet)
- Dalacin C (tablet)

Pain Management:

1. Hifenac P (tablet)
2. Combiflam (tablet)
3. Hifenac MR (tablet)
4. Brufen (tablet)
5. Ketorol DT (tablet)

27. Mostly tooth pain lasts a few hours to a week.

-> Common reasons include:

- Tooth decay
- Gum disease
- Infections
- Decay

28. URINE INFECTION: Very common.

Burning sensation or infection in any part of the urinary tract. Usually painful.

MEDICINE / DRUG:

- Oral solution (citric acid & potassium citrate)

1. K-cit (syrup)

2. Urine alkaliser (liquid)

- Disodium hydrogen citrate

3. Citralka (syrup)

4. Cital (syrup)

28. VERTIGO - Dizziness, feeling of spin or motion even when the person is not moving.

MEDICINE / DRUG

Betahistine

1. Vertin (tablet)
2. Vertihist (tablet)

Cinnarizine

3. Stugeron (tablet)
4. Diziron (tablet)
5. Vertizone (tablet)

Combination (Cinnarizine + Dimenhydrinate)

6. Vertizone (tablet)
7. Vomistop (tablet)

Meclizine

8. Bonamide (tablet)
9. Vominal (tablet)

Usually it lasts for few hours.

Most common reasons are:

1. Ear infection (inner)
2. Low blood pressure

ANTIBIOTICS

1. NITROFURANTOIN

- Nittas (tablet)
- Redfuran (tablet)

2. Amoxicillin + Potassium Clavulanate

- Augmentin 625 (tablet)
- Moxikind CV 625 (tablet)

3. Ofloxacin + Flavoxate Hydrochloride

- Zentlox UTI (tablet)
- Flavospa O (tablet)

NSAIDs can be given for pain relief.

Most common reasons of UTI are:

1. Bacteria, mostly E. coli

It usually lasts up to 3 to 5 days.

Important Disclaimer

This manual is intended for educational and informational purposes only. It focuses primarily on common over-the-counter (OTC) medications that can be recommended or dispensed by licensed pharmacists based on symptoms and need.

Note: Medications that fall under Schedule H, H1, or Schedule X as per the Drugs and Cosmetics Act and Rules (India) are prescription-only drugs. These cannot be dispensed or advised by a pharmacist without a valid prescription from a registered medical practitioner.

Pharmacists must exercise professional judgment and always refer patients to qualified doctors for any condition that:

- Is severe
- Involves prescription-only medicines
- Requires diagnostic interpretation
- Persists or worsens over time

Always follow legal and ethical pharmacy practices while prioritizing patient safety and professional integrity.